

Propagation-based phase contrast X-ray imaging with a laser-driven X-ray source in air

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Figure: Radiographic image (21x magnification) of 20dpf zebrafish taken with laser-driven x-ray source at the L2A2. Phase effects in the form of edge enhancement are clearly visible both around the zebrafish and at boundaries between internal structures within the zebrafish. TOP LEFT: A picture of the 20dpf zebrafish beside a 2€ coin. BOTTOM LEFT: A slice profile taken along the dorsal side of the zebrafish which shows the edge enhancement quantitatively.

A laser-driven x-ray source in air has been set-up and stabilized at the Laser Laboratory for Acceleration and Applications (L2A2) at the Instituto Galego de Física de Altas Enerxías (IGFAE) in the Universidade de Santiago de Compostela (USC). High-energy ultrashort laser pulses are focused onto the surface of a target material, reaching intensities greater than 10^{17} W/cm² and ionizing the target material, producing x-ray radiation. The x-ray source has a very small source size ($<10\mu\text{m}$) making it an attractive option for in-line phase-contrast x-ray imaging. Here we present a phase-enhanced x-ray image of a 20dpf zebrafish ($350\mu\text{m}$ diameter) taken with the laser x-ray source at the L2A2. The zebrafish is mounted on a thin layer ($125\mu\text{m}$) of plastic film and positioned at 3cm from the source. The image is captured using a high spatial

resolution (22LP/mm) dental image plate (Durr dental) positioned at 63cm from the source resulting in an image magnification of 21x. Several parts of the internal anatomy of the zebrafish are easily identifiable. Moreover, edge enhancement can be seen both surrounding the zebrafish as well as at various boundaries between internal structures within the zebrafish. Edge enhancement is purely a phase contrast effect and is indicative of a high degree of lateral spatial coherence in the x-ray source [1]. One of the principal challenges in setting up an in-line phase-contrast x-ray system is the proper selection of the source-to-object distance (R1) as well as the object-to-detector distance (R2) [2]. Consideration must be given to the desired object magnification (depends on R1 and R2), the dose rate fall-off with distance (depends on R1 and R2), and importantly, the coherence of the x-ray source (depends on R1) and the necessary propagation distance (R2) to be able to detect the changes in intensity induced by phase effects. To help motivate the choice of these distances, several experiments were performed using a nylon string as a phase-contrast phantom. The degree of edge enhancement was measured using different combinations of the R1 and R2 distances and analyzed to identify an optimal range of values for these distances. This phase-contrast x-ray image of a zebrafish produced by the laser-driven x-ray source at the L2A2 is the first step towards the set-up of an x-ray phase-contrast imaging system at the L2A2.

REFERENCES

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- [2] Gureyev, 2009. "Refracting Röntgen's rays: Propagation-based x-ray phase contrast for biomedical imaging".

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